

GARRI POTTER ASARIDA ZAMON VA MAKONNING IFODALANISHI

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KALIT SO'ZLAR

*Makon (voqea joyi),
Makon kategoriyasi,
Rouling.*

ANNOTATSIYA

Makon (voqea joyi) tushunchasi insonda borliqning obyektiv shakllari, makon va vaqt haqidagi tushunchalarining kengayishi, shuningdek, badiiy asarning uslubi, turi va janriga qarab o'zgarib borishi mumkin. Makon kategoriyasi asosan his-tuyg'ular tasviriga qaratilgan lirik janrda unchalik ahamiyatga ega emas.

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Qahramonlarning xatti-harakati, ularning o'y-kechinmalari, asarda tasvirlanayotgan kishilarning yurish-turishi, kiyinishi, turmush tarzi bevosita ular yashab turgan makon va zamonning ta'siri ostida bo'ladi. Masalan, naturalizm yo'nalishi vakili Emil Zolyaning asarlarida makon va zamon eng muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi, chunki yozuvchining ishonishicha, qahramonlarning qandayligini ularni o'rab turgan atrof-muhit belgilab beradi. Ba'zi hollarda esa, asardagi butun voqealar rivoji ular sodir bo'layotgan makon bilan belgilanadi. Gyustav Floberning "Bavari xonim" asari uchun Parij makon qilib olinsa noto'g'ri bo'lardi, chunki qahramonning fojiali hayoti va o'limi sababi u yashab turgan qishloq muhitiga borib taqaladi.²

¹Литературная энциклопедия. — Т.:8. М.:
гос.словарно-энцикл.изд-во "Сов.Энцикл.", 1934.

²Setting (literary device). Encyclopedia Britannica.
<http://www.britannica.com>

Yuqorida asar voqealari bizning dunyomizga o`xshash dunyoda sodir bo`lishini aytib o`tgandik, Rowling tasvirlagan dunyoning real dunyodan farqi shundaki, unda oddiy odamlar (Rowling bu o`rinda "magl" so`zini qo`llaydi) bilan birga sehrgarlar va afsungarlar ham hayot kechirishadi. Ular turli afsunlar o`qib, sehrli tayoqchalari yordamida xohlagan ishlarini bajara olishadi, ammo oddiy odamlar, ya'ni magllar o`zlari bilan yondosh yashayotgan bunday kishilar borligidan butunlay bexabar. "Chunki ular hech qachon hech nimaga e'tibor berishmaydi."

'How come the Muggles don't hear the bus?' said Harry.

*'Them!' said Stan contemptuously. 'Don' listen properly, do they? Don' look properly either. Never notice nuffink, they don'.'*³

Maktablarni solishtiradigan bo`lsak, Angliyada o`quvchilar olti yil davomida boshlang`ich maktabda tahsil olishgach, o`n bir yoshda o`rta maktabga o`tishadi. Hogvarts sehrgarlar va afsungarlar maktabiga ham sehrgarlik qobiliyati bor o`quvchilar o`n bir yoshdan qabul qilinadi. Shu o`rinda aytib o`tish joizki, Hogvarts maktabi Angliyada bir necha asr mobaynida faoliyat yuritib kelgan maktab-internatlarga o`xshash – unda ham o`quvchilar yotoqxonada turib, faqat bayram va ta'tillardagina oilalariga qaytishadi. Hogvarts sehrgarlik va afsungarlik maktabi bo`lgani uchun unda ona tili, matematika, tarix va shunga o`xshash fanlar o`rniga sehrgarlik tarixi, qora kuchlarga qarshi afsun, kelajakni bashorat qilish, sehrli ichimlik va dorilar tayyorlash kabi fanlar o`qitiladi. Maktab devorlarida osilgan

suratlarda tasvirlangan kishilar doim harakatlanib turishadi, ular o`quvchilar bilan salomlashib, ba'zida o`quvchilarning savollariga javob ham berishadi. Eng qizig`i suratdagi insonlar bir-birlarini ko`rgani borib turishadi.

*It was also very hard to remember where anything was, because it all seemed to move around a lot. The people in the portraits kept going to visit each other and Harry was sure the coats of armour could walk.*⁴

Hogvartsda qulflar o`rniga parol so`rovchi suratlar ilib qo`yilgan bo`lib, bunday eshiklarni hech qanday sehr va afsun yordamida ochishning iloji yo`q. Bundan tashqari, maktabning har yerida kezib yurgan arvohlarga ham duch kelish mumkin. Sehrgarlik tarixi fanidan ham vafot etganiga bir necha yillar bo`lgan professorning arvohi dars beradi. Maktabga ilk bor kelgan o`quvchilarni yanada hayratlantiradigan yana bir holat bu zinalarning doimiy harakat qilishidir. Maktabda bunday zinalar soni bir yuz qirq ikkita bo`lib, ularning qay paytda qay yo`nalishda harakatlanishini eslab qolish boshida biroz qiyinchilik tug`diradi. Shuningdek, maktabning shunday qismlari mavjud ediki, ularga qadam qo`yish o`quvchilarga ta'qiqlangan edi. Yana shunday xonalar bor bo`lib, ularning qayerda ekani va qanday ochish mumkinligini hatto professor o`qituvchilar ham bilishmasdi. "Maxfiy xona" ("Chamber of secrets") ham xuddi shunday yashirin xona bo`lib, u aynan qayerda joylashgani va unda nima borligidan hech kimning xabari yo`q. Ko`pchilik bu xonani faqat afsona deb o`ylab, uning borligiga ishonishmaydi.

³Rowling, J.K. Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban. – London: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC, 1999. p. 32.

⁴Rowling, J.K. Harry Potter and the Philosopher's stone. – London: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC, 1997. p. 98.

*'Slytherin, according to the legend, sealed the Chamber of Secrets so that none would be able to open it until his own true heir arrived at the school. The heir alone would be able to unseal the Chamber of Secrets, unleash the horror within, and use it to purge the school of all who were unworthy to study magic.'*⁵

Afsonaga ko`ra, maxfiy xona Salazar Slizerin tomonidan yaratilgan bo`lib, uni faqat Slizerinning haqiqiy merosxo`ri ocha oladi. Garri do`stlari Ron va Germiona yordamida maxfiy xonaga kirish yo`lini topadi hamda u yerda bir necha asrlardan buyon yashab kelayotgan dahshatli vasilisk ilonini yo`q qiladi. Hogvartsda juda ozchilikka ma`lum yana bir sehrli xona mavjud bo`lib, uni Bor-Yo`q xona ("Come and Go Room") yoki "Darkor xona" (Room of requirement") deb atashadi. Bu xonaga faqatgina kuchli ehtiyoj tug`ilgandagina kirish mumkin, shuning uchun u ba`zida paydo bo`lsa, ba`zida umuman yo`qoladi.

*It is known by us as the Come and Go Room, sir, or else as the Room of Requirement!...It is a room that a person can only enter,' said Dobby seriously, 'when they have real need of it. Sometimes it is there, and sometimes it is not, but when it appears, it is always equipped for the seeker's needs.'*⁶

Mabodo sehrgar bunday xonaga kirishga muvaffaq bo`lsa, u yerdan o`zi ehtiyoj sezgan hamma narsani topa oladi. Garri Potter tuzgan Dambldor armiyasi aynan mana shu xonada o`z mashqlarini olib borishadi. Sehrgarlar dunyosining transport vositalari ham o`ziga xos. Ular bir joydan ikkinchi joyga borish uchun asosan

transport vositalari o`rniga sehrli usullardan foydalanishadi. To`g`ri, asarning boshida Garri Hogvartsga yetib olish uchun boshqa bolalar qatori Hogvarts-ekspres tezyurar poyezdida jo`naydi, lekin poyezd o`zi yuradimi yoki boshqaruvchisi bormi bu haqida muallif biror ma`lumot bermagan. Lekin keyinroq Garri o`zi yashayotgan bu g`aroyib dunyoda uchish uchun mo`ljallangan sehrli supurgilar borligidan xabar topadi. Sehrli supurgilar sehrgarlar dunyosida mashhur bo`lsa ham, unda uzoq masofaga borish juda qiyin, shuningdek, oddiy odamlar ko`rib qolish ehtimoli kuchliligi sabab bu vositadan ko`p hollarda faqat sport o`yinlarida foydalaniladi. Afsungarlar dunyosida eng ko`p qo`llanadigan yana bir vosita bu kaminlar tarmog`i orqali kerakli joyga borish. Bunda sehrgar kaminga sehrli sayohat kukunini sepib, olov ichiga kiradi va aniq qilib kerakli joy nomini aytadi, natijada esa bir necha soniya ichida aytilgan manzilga yetib olinadi.

He took a pinch of glittering powder out of the flowerpot, stepped up to the fire and threw the powder into the flames. With a roar, the fire turned emerald green and rose higher than Fred, who stepped right into it, shouted, 'Diagon Alley!' and vanished.

*'You must speak clearly, dear,' Mrs Weasley told Harry, as George dipped his hand into the flowerpot. 'And mind you get out at the right grate ...'*⁷

Sehrgarlarning xohlagan manzillariga yetishda qo`llaydigan vositalaridan yana biri bu portaldir. Portal – sehrgarni

⁵Rowling, J.K. Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets. – London: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC, 1998. p.114.

⁶Rowling, J.K. Harry Potter and the Order of the Phoenix. – London: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC, 2003. p.343.

⁷Rowling, J.K. Harry Potter and the Chamber of Secrets. – London: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC, 1998. p.41.

oldindan mo'ljallab qo'yilgan vaqtda bir joydan boshqa joyga olib o'tishga xizmat qiladigan sehrlangan buyum. Portalning sayohat kukunidan afzallik tomoni shundaki, juda uzoq masofaga ham bir zumda yetib olish va zarur holatlarda portal yordamida bir necha kishini aniq manzilga o'tkazish mumkin. Portal birinchi marta "Garri Potter va olovli jom" kitobida tilga olinadi: *"...we use Portkeys. They're objects that are used to transport wizards from one spot to another at a prearranged time. You can do large groups at a time if you need to."*

⁸ Unda Garri va Uizlilar oilasi Sehrgarlik ishlari vazirligi tomonidan o'rnatilgan portal orqali kviddich bo'yicha jahon chempionatiga borishadi. 1994-yilgi kviddich bo'yicha jahon chempionatiga tayyorgarlik vaqtida vazirlik butun Angliya bo'ylab, strategik jihatdan muhim nuqtalarda 200dan ortiq potrallar o'rnatib chiqqan edi. Portal faqatgina vazirlik tomonidan o'rnatilishi mumkin bo'lib, sehrgarlarning o'zlari portal yaratishlari ta'qiqlangan. Kitobning xuddi shu qismida transgressiya yoki boshqacha nomi apparatsiya (apparatsiya-havoda yo'qolib, kerakli joyda paydo bo'lish) usuli ham tilga olinadi. *Harry knew that Apparating was very difficult; it meant disappearing from one place and reappearing almost instantly in another.*⁹

Ba'zi joylarda apparatsiyani qo'llash ta'qiqlangan, bundan tashqari, hamma sehrgarlar ham bu usuldan foydalana olishmaydi. Faqatgina voyaga yetgan va uzoq vaqt (bir necha oy davomida har haftalik mashg'ulotlar) mashq qilib, maxsus ruxsatnomani qo'lga kiritgan

sehrgarlargagina ruxsat berilgan. Hogvarts sehrgarlar va afsungarlar maktabida oltinchi kursni tugatgan talabalar pullik kurslarda apparatsiya qilish usullarini o'rganishadi. Kurs oxirida esa transgressiyani o'rgangan talabalar imtihon topshirib, undan muvaffaqiyatli o'tishsa, apparatsiya qilish uchun ruxsatnomani qo'lga kiritishadi. Ruxsatnomaga ega bo'lmagan va voyaga yetmagan sehrgarlar transgressiyani qo'llashsa, Sehrgarlik ishlari vazirligi tomonidan qattiq jazoga tortiladi. Chunki mabodo transgressiya muvaffaqiyatsiz amalga oshirilsa, bu sehrgarning hayotiga xavf solishi mumkin.

*'The Department of Magical Transportation had to fine a couple of people the other day for Apparating without a licence. It's not easy, Apparition, and when it's not done properly it can lead to nasty complications. This pair I'm talking about went and splinched themselves....They left half of themselves behind,' said Mr Weasley, now spooning large amounts of treacle onto his porridge*¹⁰

Bu usulni qo'llay oladigan sehrgar o'zi bilan boshqa kishini ham kerakli joyga olib o'ta oladi. Masalan, "Garri Potter va shahzoda tilsimi" qismida Albus Dambldor apparatsiya vositasida Garrini ham kerakli joyga o'zi bilan birga olib o'tadi. Bu Garrining apparatsiyadagi birinchi tajribasi edi. Xuddi shu kitobning 27-bobida Garrining o'zi mustaqil ravishda apparatsiyani qo'llaydi, bu safar Garri Dambldorni o'zi bilan birga kearkli joyga olib o'tadi.

Shunday qilib, Garri Potterda ham odamlarning ko'rinishi, kiyinishi bizning

⁸Rowling, J.K. Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire. – London: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC, 2000. p.66.

⁹Rowling, J.K.. Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire. – London: Bloomsbury Publishing PLC, 2000. p.63.

¹⁰The same source, p.63.

dunyodan farq qilmasa ham, ular ishlatadigan o'ziga xos so'zlar (afsunlar, buyum nomlari, sport turlari va hkz.), transport vositalari, pul birliklari, turli mavjudotlar va kishilarning ijtimoiy guruhlari bizning dunyodagidan butunlay farq qiladi. Sehrgarlar dunyosi oddiy odamlar dunyosi bilan yondosh, ammo uning ko'zga ko'rinmas qismi bo'lib, ba'zi hollarda oddiy insonlar sehrgarlar dunyosi hodisalariga guvoh bo'lib turishadi. Masalan, kitobning birinchi qismi boshida janob Dursli ishga ketayotib, xarita o'rganayotgan mushukka ko'zi tushadi. Keyinroq esa g'alati rido kiyib olgan to'p-to'p kishilar uning e'tiborini tortishadi, chunki bunday kiyimli kishilarni London ko'chalarida bu paytgacha uchratmagandi.

O'sha kuni mamalakat bo'ylab ko'plab boyqushlarning kunduz paytida uchib yurgani aholining e'tiborini tortadi. Aslida sehrgarlar magllar e'tiborini tortmay yashashga harakat qilishadi, chunki oddiy insonlar baribir ularni to'g'ri qabul qilishlariga ishonishmaydi. Faqatgina sehrgarlik qobiliyati bilan tug'ilgan oilalarning a'zolari va mamlakat bosh vaziri bunday dunyoning mavjudligini bilishadi, xolos.

Rouling yaratgan dunyo voqealari bizning dunyoda, biz yashayotgan davrda va asosan maktabda (garchi u sehrgarlar maktabi bo'lsa-da) bo'lib o'tishi asarning ishonarliligi va shu bilan birga o'ziga xosligini ta'minlagan

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